

Uplifting FAIR and CARE across Earth and Environmental Science (E&ES) Data

A Discussion Paper to inform the Data Targeted Discussion of the National Digital Research Infrastructure Strategy

V 3.0

Wong, M; Wyborn, L; Holewa, H.

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We acknowledge the Traditional Custodians of the land, sea and waters throughout Australia and their continuing connection to culture. We pay our respects to Elders both past and present.

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CONTENTS

Versioning History	4
Executive Summary	5
1. Context	7
A. NDRI Strategy Uplift of FAIR and CARE	7
B. Purpose of the Document	7
C. Scope of the Document: A Focus on a Subset of the Elements of CARE	8
2. Background: The Importance of FAIR and CARE in the Australian Earth and Environmental Sciences (E&ES)	9
3. Progress Towards Implementation of FAIR and Elements of CARE for the Australian Earth and Environmental Sciences (E&ES)	12
4. Challenges for Implementing FAIR and Elements of CARE in the Australian Earth and Environmental Sciences (E&ES)	15
Implementation Challenges for E&ES Researchers	15
Implementation Challenges for Australian E&ES Repositories	17
5. Recommendations to Uplift FAIR and Elements of CARE in E&ES Data	20
Overview	20
Recommendation 1: Convergence Toward a National Framework for Enabling FAIR and Elements of CARE in E&ES.	21
1.1. Converge Round Core Principles and Standards: Consider a WorldFAIR-like Approach	21
Recommendation 2. Uplifting Core Data Services and Outreach to Support FAIR and Elements of CARE for E&ES	22
2.1. Uplift Research Data Australia (RDA) Capabilities	22
2.2. Uplift Research Vocabularies Australia (RVA) Capabilities	25
2.3. Prioritise Implementation of the National PID Strategy for E&ES Research	26

Recommendation 3: Activate Leadership and Coordination to Uplift FAIR and Elements of CARE for E&ES Data	27
3.1. For FAIR	28
3.2. For CARE	28
6. Conclusions	30
7. References	31
Appendix 1: Contextual information that informed the FAIR data focused discussions of this paper	37
Appendix 2: Indigenous Data Sovereignty and Indigenous Data Governance resources	38

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Executive Summary

Outcome 3 of Australia's 2024 National Digital Research Infrastructure (NDRI) Strategy aims for consistent standards for data collection, curation, and access by 2030 through a cross-sector data management framework that supports adopting the FAIR and CARE principles. This discussion paper was prepared by the Australian Research Data Commons' (ARDC) Planet Research Data Commons to identify core challenges and recommendations for the Earth and Environmental Sciences (E&ES) in delivering Outcome 3.

The scope of this discussion focuses on how the machine-actionability of data - aligned with the FAIR Guiding Principles for Scientific Data Management and Stewardship Principles - may be uplifted across Environmental & Earth Sciences (E&ES) National Research Infrastructures (NRIs), institutes and National Collaborative Research Infrastructure Strategy (NCRIS) Facilities. In the context of the CARE Principles for Indigenous Data Governance, our focus is on those elements of implementing the CARE Principles that can be supported by improvements in FAIR data capability, specifically by improving machine-actionability of data and metadata across E&ES research.

E&ES deals with vast, diverse, heterogeneous datasets, creating significant challenges to ensure data aligns with the FAIR and the CARE Principles. Across the E&ES domains, there are different data norms, capacities and standards. There are limitations to data integration and reusability, including for data engineering and responsible AI, due to a need for more rich, standardised and machine-actionable metadata and data. Furthermore, current repository systems often have limitations in data curation and storing metadata that meets FAIR and CARE requirements. There is also limited support and few incentives for researchers and National Data Research Infrastructures to fully implement the FAIR Principles in a machine-actionable way, including capturing metadata that supports the CARE Principles.

Proposed is a combined approach that addresses the technology and social challenges of E&ES researchers and research data facilities to uplift FAIR data and elements of CARE Principles in the collection, management, curation and publication of their research input and output artefacts (e.g. data, samples, software, models, etc.). Three recommendations are presented:

Recommendation 1. Converge toward a national framework around core principles and standards for progressing FAIR and elements of the CARE Principles in E&ES. Investigate implementing a WorldFAIR Case Study approach, including the adoption/adaptation of the Cross-Domain Data Interoperability Framework (CDIF), and consider the intersection/s and complementarities between CDIF and the CARE principles.

Recommendation 2. Uplift core data services and outreach to support FAIR and elements of the CARE Principles for E&ES. The core services include Research Data Australia (RDA) (2.1), Research Vocabularies Australia (RVA) (2.2), and the implementation of the National PID Strategy (National PID services) (2.3), which are available to all researchers and research data facilities through the Australian Research Data Commons (ARDC). Uplifting these ARDC core services will also require an equivalent enhancement in the capabilities of multiple Australian individual organisations and institutions that host E&ES data, particularly for delivering comprehensive FAIR metadata from their data repository services, including for discovery through RDA.

Recommendation 3 Activate leadership and coordination to uplift FAIR and elements of CARE for E&ES data. A forum (or maybe several connected fora) will be required to collectively converge on a shared vision, identifying high-impact priorities and common needs to deliver on core principles and standards required to uplift FAIR and CARE. Existing forums may be leveraged, such as the National Earth and Environmental Science Facilities Forum and International E&ES Research Infrastructures, international scientific initiatives and unions/societies operationalising machine-actionable FAIR, and funders and publishers engaged. Working together with Indigenous-led governance structure/s and initiatives for CARE in E&ES that represent and empower Indigenous Data Governance and Indigenous Data Sovereignty for Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander researchers, organisations, and communities across Australia is essential.

The foreseen shared advantages are the enablement of machine-actionable FAIR E&ES data infrastructures and data supply chains; international competitiveness; more efficient and effective tracking of impact and return on investment; technical resource efficiency; equity of access to core FAIR E&ES data enabling services; and supporting the ethical, equitable, and responsible reuse of data, including the expression of elements of the CARE Principles for Indigenous Data Governance that can be expressed through rich machine-actionable metadata.

1. Context

A. NDRI Strategy Uplift of FAIR and CARE

‘Increasing volumes of data are being generated that are not FAIR and CARE compliant.’

National Digital Research Infrastructure (NDRI) strategy, p5.

Outcome #3 of the National Digital Research Infrastructure (NDRI) Strategy is that by 2030, Australia’s NDRI system should be ‘Consistent in its standards for data collection, curation, and access’ (NRIAG, 2024a). The NDRI Strategy recognises that the challenge for Outcome #3 is ‘Rapidly increasing rates and volumes of data are being generated across all research fields in formats that are not FAIR and CARE’ (p15). The opportunity identified is that ‘Ensuring the ever-growing body of Australia’s research data is as FAIR and CARE as possible greatly benefits the nation’s NDRI users by offering greater efficiency and fostering deeper collaboration’ (p15).

B. Purpose of the Document

This document is intended as a discussion piece to contribute to the continual deliberations, shared learning, and collaborations across Australia’s Earth and Environment Sciences in direct response to Outcome #3 of the NDRI Strategy (NRIAG, 2024a) and the Data-Targeted Discussion Summary (NRIAG, 2024b). It focuses primarily on investments in digital infrastructures required to uplift the implementation of the FAIR Guiding Principles for Scientific Data Management (FAIR Principles - Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable, Wilkinson et al., 2016). Also discussed is how improvements in FAIR data capability can support elements of the implementation of the CARE Principles for Indigenous Data Governance (CARE Principles - Collective Benefit, Authority to Control, Responsibility and Ethics, Carroll et al., 2020a) specifically through improvements in the machine-actionability of data and metadata (herein ‘(meta)data’) across E&ES research.

Recommendations are made to help address the technology and social challenges of E&ES researchers and research data facilities to uplift FAIR and elements of CARE in the collection, management, curation and publication of their research input and output artefacts (e.g. data, samples, software, models, etc.).

In the NDRI Targeted Discussion Series papers (NRIAG, 2024c), FAIR and CARE are also discussed in four of the six other Targeted Discussion Summaries. However, this paper focuses on aspects of the digital research infrastructures required to uplift the FAIR and CARE Principles for E&ES datasets as were raised across the NDRI in the Data Summary Targeted Discussion (NRIAG, 2024b). The four 'key considerations and potential investment priorities for digital research infrastructure' raised in the Data Summary document and whether they explicitly referenced FAIR or CARE were 1) Searchability and metadata (FAIR); 2) Data lifecycle management (FAIR and CARE); 3) Institutional responsibility (FAIR); and 4) International collaboration (FAIR). Sources that informed the FAIR components of this document are found in the References and Appendix 1.

C. Scope of the Document: A Focus on a Subset of the Elements of CARE

The CARE Principles encourage the consideration of both people and purpose throughout the data life cycle, reflecting the importance of data in advancing Indigenous innovation and self-determination (Carroll et al., 2020). This discussion paper was developed through the lens of research institutes, organisations and facilities. It focuses explicitly only on a subset of the technical implementation of the CARE Principles - those that can be supported by an uplift of digital research infrastructures that may enhance (meta)data and persistent identifier capabilities for the expression of Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander communities' rights and priorities. Broader Indigenous Data Governance and technical matters for the operationalisation of CARE for E&ES datasets fall outside of this paper's scope. Some resources for situating this paper within the Indigenous Data Sovereignty and Indigenous Data Governance landscape are listed in Appendix 2.

2. Background: The Importance of FAIR and CARE in the Australian Earth and Environmental Sciences (E&ES)

The growth of digital publications and the internet and digital data repositories offer new opportunities to store, curate and share/reuse data. However, due to the lack of (meta)data standardisation and online catalogues in many repositories, the data assets relevant to numerous research projects are not easily findable and reusable. Further, as most datasets are only interpretable by humans, integrating datasets from multiple sources requires enormous human efforts and data wrangling, resulting in extremely high costs and inefficiencies, as the report for the European Commission notes (PwC EU Services, 2018).

The original 2016 paper that first proposed the FAIR Principles (Wilkinson et al., 2016) emphasised the requirements for machine-actionability of all components of FAIR. This requires both the (meta)data and protocols to access and reuse data to comply with standard protocols and domain-relevant community standards that enable machine-to-machine readability and sharing of (meta)data: persistent identifiers are critical. Operationalising machine-actionability of each of the FAIR Principles, particularly those relating to the Interoperability and Reusability Principles, is complex and many papers have been published recently on this, which discuss the required investments in Research Infrastructures to support FAIR (e.g. Gregory et al., 2024; Hodson and Gregory, 2024; Jacobsen et al., 2020; Schultes et al., 2020; Schultes, 2023; Peng et al., 2024).

Figure 1 shows the four foundational characteristics of machine-actionable FAIR (PwC EU Services, 2018). Hodson and Gregory (p9, 2024) noted, 'Research data that are not sufficiently described can not be used by any form of intelligence, artificial or otherwise', and that detailed, structured metadata can play a role in the utility and precision of responsible Artificial Intelligence (AI). A recent Earth Science Information Partners (ESIP) survey showed that half of AI practitioners using environmental data spend at least 50% of their effort on data preparation (ESIP Data Readiness Cluster, n.d.).

Not having FAIR data costs the European Economy at least €10.2bn annually (PwC EU Services, 2018). There are no equivalent studies in Australia that quantify the cost. Still, it is well known that Australian researchers spend considerable time trying to find, access, integrate and reuse existing datasets that are of value to their research. The 2022-2024 project WorldFAIR: Global Cooperation on FAIR Data Policy and Practice (WorldFAIR, n.d.-a), led by the Committee on Data of the International Science Council (CODATA) (CODATA, n.d.-a) and the International Research Data Alliance (RD-A) (RD-A, n.d.), focussed on globally improving FAIR across 11 domain groups, stressed that 'too much effort and expense are still going into extracting data, ex post facto, from academic articles or supplementary materials' (p7, Hodson and Gregory, 2024).

Figure 1. The four foundational characteristics of FAIR that research data should have to maximise the value of Science. Image adapted from PwC EU Services' (2018), a representation of the FAIR guiding principles for scientific data (Wilkinson et al., 2016).

The CARE Principles (Figure 2, Carroll et al., 2020a) were created in response to production and use of open data, big data and open science, and research environments, with limited Indigenous Control are designed to be complementary to FAIR Principles and other data frameworks for equitable participation and outcomes from data access, use, reuse, and attribution in contemporary data landscapes. The CARE Principles, support Indigenous rights, and emphasize values-based relationships in data governance, moving beyond consultation to foster Indigenous-led partnerships. This approach enhances Indigenous leadership in data governance and extends FAIR criteria to both existing and newly created Indigenous data (Carroll et al., 2020b; Carroll et al., 2021). By embedding these principles, non-Indigenous institutions and government agencies can support equitable collaborations that respect Indigenous knowledge systems, protect sensitive information, and promote sustainable and ethical data practices. An articulated goal of the principles in relationship to FAIR is that 'stewards and other users of Indigenous data will 'Be FAIR and CARE' (Carroll et al., 2020a). 'Making Indigenous data FAIR within non-Indigenous institutions and government agencies is one critical objective to afford greater Indigenous participation in data governance activities' (Carroll et al. 2020b and references therein) and 'FAIR criteria should apply to already existing and newly created Indigenous data' (Carroll et al., 2021).

Figure 2. The CARE Principles for Indigenous Data Governance from Carroll et al. (2020a)

Appendix 2 lists some key resources on Indigenous Data Sovereignty and Governance matters. The CARE discussion in this paper focuses on a subset of matters - the uplift of FAIR (meta)data through machine-actionable data models, metadata, vocabularies and persistent identifiers, which can support a subset of the technical implementations of CARE. FAIR metadata is one crucial component in supporting Indigenous rights, interests, and priorities in Indigenous data. Principle E3 (Ethics for future use) states that ‘metadata should acknowledge the provenance and purpose and any limitations or obligations in secondary use inclusive of issues of consent’ (Carroll et al., 2022; Taitingfong et al., 2023). Taitingfong et al., 2023, p1 state ‘Indigenous metadata provides critical organisation and structure for Indigenous Peoples’ data to be findable, accessible, interoperable and with proper attribution, which enables governance, decision-making and cultural authority by Indigenous peoples’. A conceptual framework for an ‘Indigenous Metadata Bundle’ (Taitingfong et al., 2023) highlights the initial (non-exhaustive) metadata categories that support the recognition and inclusion of Indigenous Peoples’ data, including metadata for the expression of governance, provenance, lands and waters, protocols, as well as notices and labels for local contexts (e.g. see Anderson & Hudson 2020; Local Contexts, n.d.; Liggins et al., 2021).

3. Progress Towards Implementation of FAIR and Elements of CARE for the Australian Earth and Environmental Sciences (E&ES)

There has been considerable progress within Australia's NDRI system toward improving FAIR data in E&ES, including progress toward supporting the technical implementations of elements of CARE. For example:

- **Australia's National Collaborative Research Infrastructure Strategy (NCRIS) and related National Research Infrastructure (NRI) platforms** have already undertaken considerable work towards implementing machine-actionable FAIR. Examples include:
 - The **Terrestrial Ecosystem Research Network (TERN)** leverages standards-based linked data (TERN, n.d.-a);
 - The **Atlas of Living Australia (ALA)** utilises global standards for biodiversity metadata (ALA, n.d.);
 - **AusTraits**, which includes TERN and ALA as partners, utilises a Plant Dictionary (APD) Ontology (Faltster et al., 2021; AusTraits, n.d.);
 - The **Australian Plant Phenomics Network (APPN)** building federated data management for plant trait capture systems at nine partners (APPN, n.d);
 - **AURIN** provides standardised access to analytical tools and thousands of multidisciplinary, clean, spatialised and research-ready datasets through its Data Catalogue (AURIN, n.d.).
 - **AuScope** provides research tools, data, analytics, and support to Australia's geoscience community through its standards-compliant Data Portal (AuScope, n.d.). AuScope recently revised its (meta)data profile through its participation in the WorldFAIR Geochemistry Case Study (Wyborn et al., 2024);
 - The **Integrated Marine Observing System (IMOS)** promotes data interoperability through the use of international data standards (ISO 19115 Metadata Standard, Climate and Forecast (CF) Conventions and OGC (Open Geospatial Consortium) Standards) in the Australian Ocean Data Network (AODN) portal (AODN, n.d.) which harvests metadata from multiple sides. AODN metadata is harvested into RDA, which syndicates its metadata into schema.org. This enables nearly 11,000 Australian marine-related metadata records to be harvested into the OceanInfoHub (Ocean Infohub, n.d.), a global network of Oceans and Marine Data, which is supported by UNESCO (Buttigieg, 2024).

- Australia’s Climate Simulator, the **ACCESS-NRI (Australia’s Community Climate and Earth System Simulator - National Research Infrastructure)** supports the ACCESS framework for simulating past, present and future climate, weather and Earth systems (ACCESS-NRI, n.d.). ACCESS datasets follow internationally adopted metadata standards that address file-level metadata, including controlled vocabularies, which enable machine-actionable functionality with common climate and weather software.
- **The National Computational Infrastructure (NCI)** uplifted FAIR in their catalogue (NCI, n.d), in part through collaborative work on the AuScope 2030 Geophysics Collection (ARDC, n.d.-a; Evans et al., 2024), Earth System Grid Federation (ESGF, n.d.; Petrie et al., 2021), and other FAIR data projects.
- **Australian Government-supported (Non-NCRIS) E&ES data infrastructures** in E&ES are uplifting FAIR data; for example, States and Territories are delivering data to machine-actionable standards through the Biodiversity Data Repository (BDR) (BDR, n.d.) and Australian National Soil Information System (ANSIS) (ANSIS, n.d.).
- **Indigenous-led data infrastructure implementations at the community and nationally** support Indigenous Governance of Data and FAIR data. Examples include the ARDC-supported, Indigenous Data Network-led ‘Improving Indigenous Research Capabilities’ technical and social architectures and the Language Data Commons of Australia (LDaCA). There will likely be cross-learnings from these Humanities, Arts, and Social Sciences focused initiatives with E&ES. In E&ES, the National Earth and Environmental Science Facilities Forum (NEESFF) (Rawling et al., 2023) agreed that a consistent approach to the management and governance of Indigenous Data was desired. In response, the ARDC-supported *Governance of Indigenous Data Learning Partnerships* project has recently been initiated to improve the understanding of the requirements to manage Indigenous data appropriately, aligned with good practice such as the CARE principles.

FAIR data for cross-domain interoperability is still very challenging for E&ES. Community consultations for the Planet Research Data Commons (‘Planet RDC’) of the Australian Research Data Commons (ARDC) (Levett, 2022) highlighted that the top-ranked data challenges and opportunities in E&ES research are related to FAIR data challenges - that is, the ability to discover relevant datasets online that are curated and able to be integrated, with clear protocols for access and reuse (Figure 3).

DATA CHALLENGES IN ORDER OF PRIORITY

Figure 3. Ranked data challenges in order of priority from the Planet RDC consultation with National Stakeholders through discussions and roundtables (Australian Research Data Commons, 2022).

Supporting the Planet RDC consultations findings (Figure 3), the WorldFAIR project argued that current research data infrastructures are still dominated by a ‘bibliographic approach’ to data stewardship, in which datasets are treated like a book on a shelf in a library and managed and discovered via a catalogue with minimum metadata: the user must download the data and assess it locally to see if can be reused and fit their purpose. Then, users can spend days wrangling formats and harmonising vocabularies to aggregate multiple datasets.

In their second policy brief to the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) (Hodson and Gregory, 2024), the WorldFAIR project noted that realising the vision and the benefits of FAIR data, particularly automating data integration and provisioning responsive and fine-grained data access, requires a shift from a ‘bibliographic’ data stewardship practice to a data engineering practice. In the data engineering approach, far richer and more comprehensive standardised (meta)data is required to enable machine-to-machine access protocols and the selection of specific variables of interest across multiple online datasets. This will allow recombination in targeted ways, enabling data products and AI applications to work on nationally aggregated datasets. The EOSC policy brief also noted that the change to machine-actionable data ‘is one of a magnitude which will necessitate considerable resourcing, investment, and upskilling; but it will also achieve significant benefits’ (p8, Hodson & Gregory, 2024).

4. Challenges for Implementing FAIR and Elements of CARE in the Australian Earth and Environmental Sciences (E&ES)

Uplifting the implementation of the FAIR Principles, including enabling a subset of the technical implementation of CARE Principles through the use of metadata and persistent identifiers to reflect Indigenous rights, authority and ethical considerations in Australian E&ES science, is challenging. There are many diverse E&ES domains, each with differing individual expectations, needs, capacities, and data handling norms for delivering FAIR data. In addition, E&ES scientific research operates on a wide range of scales. By number, most researchers form the 'long-tail' of science (Heidorn, 2008) - undertaking research on, or producing large numbers of small-volume datasets (measured in MBs) on local PCs and cloud infrastructures. By volume, leading-edge competitive research in climate, satellite and geophysics is pushing exascale, requiring machine-to-machine integration of high-resolution national and global datasets that are petabytes in volume and need specialised data infrastructures to create, curate and update data over the longer term.

Because of this diversity and heterogeneity, E&ES researchers across Australia struggle to discover, access, and integrate data assets easily. It is impossible to integrate data at scale without sufficient metadata that clearly states provenance, including for multiple downstream subsamples and derivative data products.

Likewise, researchers who publish data have grappled with the basics of describing their datasets with rich, machine-actionable metadata and vocabularies to make their data FAIR and more CARE-enabled. In many E&ES research areas, the required community-agreed domain-specific standards and vocabularies still need to be created.

Implementation Challenges for E&ES Researchers

These include:

- 1) Data can be hard to find, as mandatory metadata can be limited and often non-standardised. For example, spatial location is optional in the registry interchange format Collections and Services (RIF-CS) schema (ARDC, n.d.-b) used by Research Data Australia and in the Data Scheme (Office of the National Data Commissioner, n.d.) for sharing Australian Government data. Location is critical to E&ES research. Furthermore, without location, it is challenging for Indigenous Rights and interests to be expressed with data, particularly legacy data. Likewise, only minimal keywords are recommended by either of the above schemas. Without rich keywords, particularly those relevant to E&ES, data discovery is limited - researchers need to manually check each dataset in a catalogue to see if it is pertinent to their research.

- 2)** For FAIR machine-to-machine interoperability for E&ES datasets, FAIR vocabularies should be used to describe metadata (e.g. keywords) and data. However, researchers struggle to find, select or publish the vocabulary that best describes their data online. There are now so many online vocabulary registers that the question becomes where to search. Even the most basic environmental feature vocabulary is hard to find. This is complicated by the duplication of vocabularies (noted in the Research Vocabularies Australia (RVA) A review, Cox and Yu, 2019). Once a term is discovered, researchers and NRIs can struggle to evaluate whether it is fit for purpose (e.g. licensed for reuse from an authoritative source) and whether the term is endorsed by an Authoritative scientific organisation (e.g. International Science Union/Society/Association, National Standards authority, etc.). Then, there is the fundamental question of whether the vocabulary will persist: is there a formal organisation supporting the governance and update of the vocabulary, and does it have sustainable funding?
- 3)** For FAIR, many E&ES datasets do not record provenance: at best, it is recorded in unstructured text descriptions. Although provenance metadata schemas and ontologies are available (e.g., PROV-O (Lebo, Sahoo and McGuinness, 2013)), they are not commonly used because there are not the supporting infrastructures or workflows for researchers to deploy them easily. It is essential to know the provenance of a data product for transparency and reproducibility of research, including meta-analysis.
- 4)** For FAIR, metadata elements should include Identifiers for individuals (e.g. ORCID) and Organisations (e.g. ROR) to be able to give credit to researchers, institutions and funders who supported the initial sample and data acquisition and recognition for repositories that store and manage the primary field samples and field observational data, including large volume satellite, drone and airborne surveys. Provenance, supported by identifiers, is critical for funders to measure usage, impact and derived value not only from their original investments, but also measure further uptake and reuse in downstream datasets and products.
- 5)** For FAIR and CARE, careful versioning of individual E&E datasets, with each published version having a globally unique, resolvable PID (Klump et al., 2021), is essential for machine-actionable traceability of the provenance of any dataset. This helps trace datasets and their derivatives (e.g. maps, models) to evaluate their appropriate reuse and potential.

- 6) For FAIR and CARE, many E&ES datasets have access and licensing/reuse constraints. Since access constraints and licensing are not documented as machine-actionable metadata (including for Indigenous Cultural and Intellectual Property (ICIP) rights), in many cases, each dataset has to be manually checked to see if it can be reused. Unfortunately, many researchers do not understand data licensing well, and in some areas, licensing and access constraints are ignored, either deliberately or unintentionally. Researchers unnecessarily restrict some datasets, whilst individual research institutions' differing intellectual property (IP) and licensing requirements confuse researchers and make it hard to comply with FAIR's Accessible and Reusable principles, including machine-actionable licences.
- 7) For CARE, it supports Indigenous rights to their data, and addresses ethical, governance,, challenges which are focused on Indigenous-control, benefit-sharing, and respect. Metadata for CARE should reflect Indigenous governance to their data (including data ownership, provenance, protocols, and permissions for access, use and reuse), Indigenous Cultural Authority and governance of Indigenous data), which are not necessarily addressed by FAIR (see Taitingfong et al., 2023 for a conceptual framework for an 'Indigenous Metadata Bundle'). Metadata should express the rights of the Traditional Owners on whose lands the primary samples and data were collected and linked to any downstream subsamples or derivative datasets. These complex challenges exist within the short research lifecycle and academic time pressures of researchers, and the budget and capacity of current infrastructures and organisations. Further, governance frameworks are required to build Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander decision-making into such metadata decisions, and building the Indigenous data workforce is required to realise inherent Indigenous rights, opportunity and benefit-sharing in E&ES Indigenous Data.

Implementation Challenges for Australian E&ES Repositories

These include:

- 1) For FAIR, many institutional and government repositories that host E&ES data need a data asset management system and an online catalogue containing all their data assets. Even if they do, there is 1) insufficient digital infrastructure to support richer metadata for expressing the FAIR Principles in a machine-actionable way, particularly for discoverability, as noted by Gregory et al. (2024) and 2) researchers may not know it exists or lodge records to it.
- 2) For FAIR, curating E&ES datasets in repositories, including compliance with the relevant domain-specific requirements, is essential if a dataset is to be validated and ingested to ensure conformance to FAIR. If the data is incorporated into national high-resolution datasets (see the Department of Education, Skills and Employment, 2021), existing datasets must be upgraded as hardware, software, and information standards (including metadata schemas and vocabularies) evolve. This is critical for longitudinal E&ES research, where time series datasets are collected over many decades of research.

- 3) For FAIR, only a few data repositories hosting E&ES datasets and physical samples relevant to the research community follow national or international standards for their data assets, resulting in siloed data that are discoverable online only if they have a web-accessible catalogue. Even if a repository does have an online catalogue, it may not use cross-domain (meta)data standards; each repository has to be searched individually to discover relevant assets. Further, if the data discovered does not use standard formats or document the vocabularies used to describe their data, it is very time-consuming to integrate multiple local and regional datasets into national high-resolution datasets. The 2021 National Research Infrastructure Roadmap (Department of Education, Skills and Employment, 2021) noted that resources technology research should be underpinned by research infrastructure that includes ‘integrated national geo-mapping data including high-resolution geoscience data and information about the potential mineral, energy and groundwater resources concealed beneath the surface’. Currently, the creation of such high-resolution datasets requires searching across multiple Commonwealth, State and Territory Government Catalogues, the CSIRO Data Access Portal (CSIRO, n.d.), and multiple institutional repositories for relevant datasets, as not all of these sources are currently harvested by Research Data Australia (RDA) (RDA, n.d.).
- 4) For FAIR, some E&ES funders or researchers want their data to be in FAIR-compliant repositories to meet research ambitions and funder requirements. To achieve this, Australian researchers increasingly use overseas domain repositories such as EarthChem (EarthChem, n.d.), EarthScope (EarthScope, n.d.), and Pangea (Pangea, n.d.), which meet domain standards for data preservation and curation, as Australia does not have the long-term equivalents researchers seek.
- 5) For FAIR, data curation is a resource-intensive process, and many Australian research data repositories cannot offer comprehensive curation due to financial constraints. Even with CoreTrustSeal certification (CoreTrustSeal, n.d.), repositories may still ingest metadata and datasets exactly as submitted, without independent peer review or curation.
- 6) For FAIR, there is little career reward or incentive for researchers in Australia to comply fully with FAIR from either funders or publishers. For example, most publishers now only demand that any dataset that underpins a scholarly publication has a Digital Object Identifier (DOI) and is stored in a repository. This results in researchers using generic repositories such as Figshare, Zenodo, and Dryad, and many institutes and publishers specifically request that researchers deposit datasets into their generic repositories. These can require little more than a title and abstract, meaning the datasets are not FAIR, as generic repositories cannot provide domain-level curation (e.g. Hanel, 2022). NCRIS requires that ‘data generated, created, captured or stored by NCRIS funded projects will be made available to the broader research community based on the FAIR Principles, appropriately implemented for individual research communities’ (Department of Education, 2021). Likewise, FAIR is encouraged by the Australian Research Council, National Health and Medical Research Council, and Universities Australia (NHMRC, 2019). However, no enforcement or other incentivisation has encouraged researchers to make their data FAIR.

- 7) For CARE, the AIATSIS Code of Ethics for Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander Research states that, amongst other responsibilities, ‘Institutions with responsibility for data access and use policies or design and management of data ecosystems should adopt Indigenous Data Sovereignty and governance principles’ and that ‘researchers must be aware of and apply FAIR and CARE (AIATSIS, 2020). Yet, like FAIR, guidance and incentivisation from institutions, publishers and funders for CARE operationalisation is required, including guidance to researchers from repositories on how CARE operationalisation is supported through the data lifecycle. O’Brien et al. (2024) define and prioritise sets of activities that E&ES repositories can take to better adhere to the CARE Principles. For CARE, the development of data curation workflows requires the engagement of appropriate Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander organisations to consider the needs of heterogeneous communities including nations, clans and kinship systems. Some data engineering challenges include supporting cultural authority to control, particularly for culturally sensitive data, and the mapping and re-mapping of Indigenous geospatial boundaries. Appropriate partnerships with Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander individuals and groups — including governing bodies, committees, communities, clans, and Indigenous knowledge holders — is crucial for ensuring effective preservation, long-term maintenance, and the meaningful curation of data assets by repositories. Their input enhances data quality and serves as a fundamental mechanism for upholding Indigenous Data Sovereignty principles and Indigenous Data Governance and within data ecosystems.

5. Recommendations to Uplift FAIR and Elements of CARE in E&ES Data

Overview

The NDRI Strategy recommends a ‘sector-wide data management framework that supports adopting the FAIR and CARE principles nationally’ (Outcome #3) (NRIAG, 2024a). Australia cannot solve this challenge in isolation. In an open science world (UNESCO, 2022), global solutions that respect rights and local contexts around data are required. A combined approach is needed to converge across E&ES research data facilities that address technology and social challenges and link them with international standards efforts (Figure 4). We detail three recommendations for uplifting core FAIR and CARE enabling services for E&ES and enacting social mechanisms for convergence toward a framework that supports national machine-actionable FAIR and elements of the CARE Principles that FAIR implementations can support.

Figure 4. Recommendations for uplifting FAIR and elements of the CARE Principles that FAIR implementations can support across Earth and Environmental Sciences (E&ES) researchers and National Research Infrastructures (NRIs). This includes enacting social mechanisms for convergence toward a framework that supports national implementation and FAIR enabling services. [E2SIP](#) - Australasian Earth and Environmental Science Information Partners (Murdoch et al., 2021).

Recommendation 1: Convergence Toward a National Framework for Enabling FAIR and Elements of CARE in E&ES.

1.1. Converge Round Core Principles and Standards: Consider a WorldFAIR-like Approach

Convergence around core principles and standards for progressing FAIR and elements of CARE enabled through FAIR data could be enabled by the adoption of a WorldFAIR-like approach, which would support the following:

a. For uplifting FAIR

- i) Investigate the adoption/adaptation and potential contribution to the Cross Domain Interoperability Framework (CDIF) (Figure 5) (Gregory et al., 2024).
- ii) Coalesce around vocabularies and standards from local siloes to national and preferably international best practices.
- iii) Support and communicate learnings from exemplary efforts in standards-based data engineering, where datum/variables of interest (not only metadata) can be accessed, provenance traced, and data harmonised in a machine-actionable way within and across domains to tackle complex/transdisciplinary problems.

b. Specifically relating to Indigenous Data

- i) Consider the intersection/s and complementarities between CDIF and the CARE Principles for Indigenous Data Governance
- ii) Consider emergent Indigenous Data Standards (e.g. see IEEE Standards Association, n.d.) and metadata content (e.g. see Anderson & Hudson 2020; Local Contexts, n.d.; Liggins et al., 2021; Taitingfong et al., 2023).
- iii) Support Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander-endorsed vocabularies.

Figure 5: Potential future cross-domain interoperability framework (CDIF) profiles proposed in WorldFAIR project output (based on Gregory et al., 2024).

Recommendation 2. Uplifting Core Data Services and Outreach to Support FAIR and Elements of CARE for E&ES

2.1. Uplift Research Data Australia (RDA) Capabilities

RDA is a domain-agnostic national data discovery service that provides a valuable tool for searching and discovering E&ES data. It delivers descriptions of data, software, and research services from over one hundred Australian research organisations, government agencies, and cultural institutions. RDA provides a one-stop-shop for supporting domain-neutral meta(data) discovery and sharing data online. Currently, RDA aggregates metadata from 102 contributing organisations (~220,000 records in total).

RDA does not store any data; it only harvests metadata. Then, it links back to the source datasets of the contributing organisations, which are responsible for storing, curating, and making them accessible. For this reason, it is not just a matter of uplifting RDA to store the richer metadata required for compliance with machine-actionable FAIR; the metadata profiles at the contributing organisations also have to be uplifted, and workflows adapted to capture the additional metadata.

Supporting and enhancing the use of RDA for E&ES makes good technological and financial sense. As facilities and domain initiatives build more data hubs and domain portals for specific purposes, RDA relieves the burden of facilities and domain initiatives to develop and maintain their own centralised metadata aggregation. It does not compete with research data facilities, government data portals, or products. From RDA, syndicating systems such as Google dataset search and Ocean Infohub (Ocean Infohub, n.d.) harvest metadata to cross-domain standards in schema.org (schema.org, n.d.) and JSON-LD (JSON-LD.org, n.d.) (as recommended by the CDIF). This enhances linkage, search and discovery of data across the web through Google search and Scholix (Burton et al. 2017; Khan et al., 2020) and catalyses cross-domain data integration and research collaborations for E&ES research, hence R&D impact.

Areas for enhancement of RDA for uplifting the FAIR and CARE for E&ES include:

- a.** For FAIR, it is not just a matter of uplifting RDA to include the richer metadata required to enhance machine-actionability. Each of the organisations/research institutions that contribute to RDA will also need to be uplifted to support the capture of the additional rich metadata. This would require RDA and all repositories storing E&ES data sets to uplift to modern international metadata standards such as those outlined in the cross-domain interoperability framework (CDIF, Gregory et al., 2024) including schema.org (schema.org, n.d), Document Discovery Initiative–Cross Domain Integration (DDI-CDI, DDI Alliance, n.d.), Object Relational Description Language (ORDL) Information Model 2.2 (Iannella and Villata, 2018) and the Digital Catalog Vocabulary (D-CAT; Albertoni et al., 2024) (Figure 5). Such richer metadata would support FAIR in E&ES data and enhance cross-domain data discovery, interoperability and reusability, as RDA could leverage rich domain-relevant metadata for datasets from organisations that follow best practices for data engineering for their domain. In addition, the ability of RDA to syndicate its metadata to standardised schemas for consumption by external services (e.g., Data Citation Index on the Web of Science (Clarivate, n.d.), Schema.org (Schema.org, n.d.) and Scholix (Burton et al., 2017; Khan et al., 2020) makes RDA a fundamental and powerful component of the Australian National Digital Research Infrastructure that facilitates the inclusion of Australian datasets in International networks. This was illustrated by the automated consumption of Australian marine datasets from RDA into the International Oceans InfoHub (Buttigieg et al., 2024).

- b.** The FAIR Principles specific to Interoperability and Reuse emphasise the importance of domain-relevant vocabularies, standards and formats (e.g. Schultes, 2023; Peng et al., 2024). Recording and capturing domain-relevant standards and semantic resources in metadata increases the richness of that metadata, which in turn increases the ability of machines and AI tools to assess whether the dataset is relevant to a particular research study. Structuring these domain-relevant standards around generic abstractions and ontologies that exploit common scientific data patterns can further enhance the interoperability and reuse of data. Generic abstractions of great importance to E&ES data include the OGC Abstract Specification Topic 20: Observations, measurements and samples (Scheidt and Rinne, 2023); also published as ISO 19156:2023 Geographic information — Observations, Measurements and Samples (ISO, 2023)) and the World Wide Web Consortium (W3C) Semantic Sensor Network Ontology (Cox et al., 2024).
- c.** For FAIR, the E&ES community should define and implement a minimum metadata profile (such as from CDIF) that maximises FAIR-ness, including minimum rights and access. This will assist in uplifting FAIR across Australian E&ES research institutions and relevant government agencies.
- d.** For FAIR, although RDA allows the recording of spatial coordinates to enable place-based assessments of all E&ES data available on a specific geographic area, many institutional and government source repositories aggregated into RDA do not or cannot record this. Investments must address uplifting E&ES data repositories across Australia to spatially enable their data catalogues and ensure they follow international standards.
- e.** For CARE, metadata elements supporting the expression of elements of CARE (see the framework of Taitingfong et al., 2023) can be guided by Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander communities and data initiatives. For example, there are the implementation of standards that can be learnt from nationally (e.g. through the Indigenous Data Network IDN - Indigenous Research Capabilities Project) and internationally (e.g. in collaborations through Global Indigenous Data Alliance (GIDA, GIDA-Global, n.d.) including the development of metadata blocks using elements of CDIF such as schema.org (schema.org, n.d.), DDI-CDI (DDI Alliance, n.d.), ORDL (Iannella and Villata, 2018) and D-CAT (Albertoni et al., 2024).

2.2. Uplift Research Vocabularies Australia (RVA) Capabilities

RVA (RVA, n.d.) is a national vocabulary service that enables the discovery and reuse of controlled vocabularies, including those used by E&ES data NRIs and researchers. These vocabularies allow data discovery, linking, harmonisation and integration in a way that humans and machines understand when used in metadata, datasets and services. This machine-understandability is critical for AI readiness. RVA is an essential service for NRI organisations and researchers who do not have the capacity, inclination, or skill set to implement and maintain a vocabulary service. RVA enables NRIs and researchers to create and maintain vocabularies that comply with international standards, including the Simple Knowledge Organisation System (SKOS, n.d.). RVA is domain agnostic, supporting interdisciplinary research and essential given the broad scientific domains of E&ES. Currently, RVA enables access to over 353 vocabularies from the research, government or industry sectors relevant to Australian researchers.

Areas for enhancement and outreach for the utilisation of RVA by NRIs and researchers to improve the utility of vocabularies include:

- a. Search and discovery across vocabulary/ontology registries, including RVA, Australian Government and state agencies vocabulary services, the IDN Vocabularies (Indigenous Data Network, n.d.), and relevant E&ES International vocabulary/ontology services such as the UK National Environmental Research Council (NERC) Vocabulary Server (NERC, n.d.), the Semantic Web for Earth and Environmental Terminology (SWEET) Ontology (McGibney et al., 2022) and the Environmental Ontology (ENVO) (Buttigieg et al., 2013).
- b. Support for the discovery, publishing and maintenance of the fundamental concepts required to describe E&ES data, such as feature type and property vocabularies.
- c. Pathways for data providers to publish informatics resources in addition to controlled vocabularies. These include taxonomies, mappings, ontologies, subject heading systems, CF Conventions (CF Conventions, n.d.), identifier schemas, and other metadata schemas required to describe research input and output artefacts.
- d. Communities and scientific domain capability development in expressing relationships between vocabulary terms and their sources.
- e. Additional easy-to-use user interfaces and workflows for vocabulary creation to help researchers and NRIs incorporate best practices without knowledge of standards for data semantics.
- f. Recommendations on essential metadata to document a vocabulary. These should include DOI, provenance and owner, and information on governance and sustainability (including endorsement (e.g. by International Science Unions, Societies, Associations and Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander communities), funding and maintenance).

- g.** Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander groups and communities should be able to lead Indigenous data governance elements within vocabularies as they require, including ICIP, worldviews, people, and purpose.
- h.** Potential for allocation of Persistent Identifiers (PIDs) within the workflow of vocabulary creation, including at the resource level (i.e. DOIs for citing a vocabulary and vocabulary concepts).

2.3. Prioritise Implementation of the National PID Strategy for E&ES Research

Persistent identifiers (PIDs) are a vital component of the FAIR Principles. As stated in the National PID Strategy (Australian Research Data Commons, 2024): ‘PIDs can maximise the value of the investments in our research and innovation ecosystem by enhancing research through reducing duplication and improving research reproducibility, provenance and attribution; catalysing innovation and impact through the use of PIDs, which apply across sectors, disciplines, domains and borders; making the research and innovation ecosystem more efficient, including through reducing administrative burden; optimising the research and innovation ecosystem through facilitating understanding of how elements of the ecosystem, including investment, use, outputs, outcomes and impact, relate to one another’. The ARDC offers Australian research sector PID services for DOIs, Handles, International Generic Sample Numbers (IGSN) and Research Activity Identifiers (RAiD). These PIDs are all international standards provided in partnership with international PID providers.

Furthering the use of PIDs in the E&ES community will ensure standards and consistency in identifying and tracking E&ES research. PIDs will assist with discovering and appropriately reusing FAIR data and data described with CARE metadata and meet researchers' and funders' attribution and credit needs. Applying PIDs in E&ES will exemplify their benefits to the broader Australian research community.

PID uplift in the E&ES community will involve:

- a.** Integration of the ability to mint, curate and manage PIDs into E&ES research infrastructures and institutional infrastructures to manage E&ES research data artefacts (data, software, samples, models, instruments, etc) and related entities (researchers, organisations).
- b.** Agreement on the standard E&ES metadata fields and terms to be included when minting DOIs.
- c.** Integration of PIDs into existing research workflows for managing data and artefacts by E&ES researchers.
- d.** Integration of PIDs into existing research workflows for managing data and artefacts by E&ES researchers.
- e.** Uptake of RAiD, an ISO standard and ARDC PID service offering PIDs for research projects, within a metadata envelope that includes FAIR and CARE-enabling metadata.
- f.** Guidance by Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander priorities around the implementation of PIDs for the expression of roles, rights and interests of Indigenous Australians in data.

Recommendation 3: Activate Leadership and Coordination to Uplift FAIR and Elements of CARE for E&ES Data

A forum (or maybe several connected fora) will be required to collectively converge on a shared vision, identifying high-impact priorities and common needs to deliver on core principles and standards required to uplift FAIR and CARE. Such a proposal will facilitate:

- a.** A collaborative cross-sector approach is needed to assist in identifying high-impact priorities and common needs and the critical levers that will drive high-level system changes that are maintainable and sustainable. This encompasses the definition of critical success factors, clear accountabilities, and shared metrics to ensure the principles are effectively translated into practical, community-driven actions, including:
 - i) Coordination through an existing national forum like the National Earth and Environmental Science Facilities Forum (NEESFF) (Rawling et al., 2023) and the supporting Information Standards Advisory Panel (ISAP) (Farrington et al., 2024).
 - ii) Working together with Indigenous-led governance structure/s and initiatives for CARE in E&ES that represent and empower Indigenous Data Governance and Indigenous Data Sovereignty for Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander researchers, organisations, and communities across Australia is essential.
- b.** Identification of targeted domain and cross-domain case studies that more directly and collectively address the National Digital Research Infrastructure Strategy, Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islanders' and researchers' most pressing and impactful collective needs.
- c.** Engagement of funders and publishers to help drive incentives for researchers to engage in good practice. For example, as suggested by PWC in Europe, funders can 'appraise the importance of FAIR and include, where relevant, compliance to the FAIR principles as a condition for researchers to obtain funding' (PWC EU Services, 2018).
- d.** Ensuring that use cases contribute effectively to learnings applicable across the E&ES domains and enabling core data infrastructure, tooling and automation workflows to be available and re-usable nationally.

3.1. For FAIR

International Collaboration is essential to maintain the currency and impact of Australian FAIR data. However, due to geographical location, time zone constraints, high costs of International travel, and concerns on carbon footprints, Australians have difficulty directly participating in international standards-setting organisations and communities. This could be alleviated by:

- a. A specific Australian-based community supported to run in parallel with an international equivalent. For example, the Australasian Earth and Environmental Science Information Partners (E2SIP) cluster (Murdoch et al., 2021) was formed to help connect Australians with relevant US-based ESIP clusters (e.g. Physical Sample Curation, Information Quality, Data Readiness, Coalition for Publishing of Data in the Earth and Space Sciences (COPDESS)) and others described in Collaboration Areas (ESIPfed, n.d.-a)).
- b. Fostering and financially supporting direct links with international E&ES research infrastructure equivalents, such as ENVRI (Environmental Research Infrastructures) Community (ENVRI, n.d.), European Plate Observing System (EPOS, n.d.), Global Ecosystem Research Infrastructure (Loescher et al., 2022), Earth System Grid Federation (ESGF, n.d.), EarthScope Consortium (EarthScope, n.d.), Earth Science Information Partners (ESIPfed.org, n.d.-b), and Global Soil Partnership (GSP, FAO.org, n.d.).
- c. Developing direct links with domain-specific equivalents in E&ES within the context of International Cross Domain data initiatives such as CODATA (CODATA, n.d.), WorldFAIR Plus (WorldFAIR, n.d.-d), and many of the working and interest groups of the Research Data Alliance (RD-A) (RD-A, n.d.-a) (e.g. the Improving Earth and Environmental Sciences Data Community of Practice (RD-A, n.d.-b)).

3.2. For CARE

Acknowledging that FAIR implementations of CARE sit within the broader data ecosystem, across which there is a need for:

- a. Raising 'widespread Indigenous data literacy and capability by allocating resources for Indigenous workforce expansion and investing in digital infrastructure and systems aligned with Indigenous priorities' (MaiaM nayri Wingara, the Australian Indigenous Governance Institute and the Lowitja Institute, 2023).
- b. FAIR implementations of CARE are to be guided by Indigenous Australian priorities and informed through Indigenous-led initiatives. There are Indigenous-led data-related initiatives within Australia, including the Indigenous Data Network (IDN) and MaiaM nayri Wingara (MaiaM nayri Wingara, n.d.), the ARDC-supported *Governance of Indigenous Data Learning Partnerships*

project across E&ES, as well as international initiatives including the Global Indigenous Data Alliance (GIDA, GIDA-Global, n.d.).

- c.** Links with First Nations-led E&ES forums such as the Geological Society of Australia (GSA) Geoscience Indigenous Collaboration and Engagement Specialist Group (GICE) (GICE, n.d.), the Indigenous Engagement Working Group (IEWG) of the Environmental Institute of Australia and New Zealand (EIANZ; EIANZ, n.d), and data infrastructure fora/standards initiatives such as the Earth Science Information Partners (ESIP) Sustainable Data Management Cluster (ESIPFed, n.d.-c).

6. Conclusions

The paper outlines an approach for an integrated framework, combining social and technical considerations, toward consistent standards for data collection, curation and access to ensure Australia's growing body of E&ES data is FAIR and more CARE enabled. Anticipated benefits of this approach include:

- 1) Enabling the FAIR data supply chain:** Comprehensive interlinked digital holdings across highly diverse E&ES domains (and cross-domain) and systems, both nationally and internationally (e.g. Google Datasets, European Open Science Cloud (EOSC), etc.) through reusing existing international standard practices, linked open data and web architectural principles.
- 2) International competitiveness:** Strengthening Australia's national digital data research infrastructure and positioning Australia as an international leader in responsible and efficient data management in E&E scientific research. This would also make Australia a significant player in standardised global E&ES data networks.
- 3) Responsibility:** Data documented with rich, machine-actionable metadata to support ethical, equitable and responsible data reuse, including for Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander expression of elements of the CARE Principles for Indigenous Data Governance.
- 4) Impact:** Firstly, enhanced ability to quantitatively measure impact and return on research investment through more efficient and effective tracking and, secondly, broader outreach of Australian E&ES datasets and research (e.g. through Google search, Scholix, etc.).
- 5) Technical and resource efficiency:** A solid base of technical infrastructure for E&ES data service providers to build more specialised data services and products, eliminating the overhead of each provider needing to build and maintain hundreds of bilateral data exchanges.
- 6) Equity of access to core FAIR data enabling services:** Diversified participation in the data ecosystem through providing FAIR data services to institutes, organisations, researchers and individuals who would otherwise not be able to either deliver their metadata, data and vocabularies in standard formats and democratically access data that already exists.

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Appendix 1: Contextual information that informed the FAIR data focused discussions of this paper.

- 1. The National Digital Research Infrastructure Strategy** - The NDRI Strategy provides a user-centric vision for Australia's digital research infrastructure (NRIAG, 2024a).
- 2. ARDC Planet RDC Consultations** - The Australian Research Data Commons (ARDC) consulted with over 250 researchers, decision-makers and industry regarding data challenges faced in the Earth and Environmental Sciences (Levett, 2022).
- 3. The WorldFAIR Project (2022 - 2024)** - The project (WorldFAIR, n.d.-a) brought together an international perspective of enabling, with the vision of enabling community agreements around interoperability and encouraging the identification and adoption of common standards. The project's focus was enabling machine-actionable FAIR, particularly for the Interoperability and Reusability Principles. Australians led the Social Sciences Case Study (Australian National University, WorldFAIR, n.d.-b) and the Geochemistry Case Study (AuScope, WorldFAIR, n.d.-c).
- 4. Australian FAIR data symposia and workshops**, including CODATA-DDI Alliance Dagstuhl Workshop 2021 (Australia) (Brownlee, 2021; CODATA, n.d.-b) and the Australian 2022 (Wong et al., 2023) and 2023 (Australian Research Data Commons, 2023) Vocabulary Symposia and Workshops. These documents provide identification of challenges and opportunities for progressing vocabularies used to describe and harmonise data in the Australian Context.
- 5. Integrated Earth 2023** - Participants from the five Earth systems (geosphere, biosphere, cryosphere, hydrosphere, and atmosphere) from across Australia's major E&ES facilities made recommendations to achieve combined objectives for data integration, integrated modelling approaches, and scientific collaboration (TERN, n.d.-b).
- 6. The 2021 NCRIS National Research Infrastructure Roadmap** highlighted the need for integrated national geo-mapping data to provide high-resolution geoscience data and information and enable data interoperability (Department of Education, Skills and Employment, 2022).
- 7. 2030 Geophysics Collection Project** co-invested in by ARDC, NCI, AuScope, and TERN, created a new high-performance dataset and a community platform that allows researchers to combine HPC, high-resolution datasets and agile software workflows. The project also provided a pathway to enable Australia's national geophysical datasets to meet the FAIR data principles, achieve sustainability and contribute to innovative high-impact research (ARDC, n.d.-a; Evans et al., 2024).
- 8. Enabling FAIR data in Geochemistry through the WorldFAIR Project** - This document summarises four major reports that advocate for urgency to publish current existing protocols, vocabularies, etc., online at local, national, and international levels to ultimately form focused international communities of practice to coalesce on global data agreements (Wyborn et al., 2024).

Appendix 2: Indigenous Data Sovereignty and Indigenous Data Governance resources.

Listed are some key resources for further contextualising this discussion paper within the broader Indigenous Data Sovereignty and the Governance of Indigenous Data landscape:

Improving Indigenous Research Capabilities Framework release is upcoming led by the Indigenous Data Network (IDN).

From exploitation to empowerment: how researchers can protect Indigenous peoples' rights to own and control their data. A Nature Index 'By changing how contracts are done, institutions can move away from exploitative research practices.'

Maiam nayri Wingara Indigenous Data Sovereignty principles are outlined through the Indigenous Data Sovereignty Communique (Maiam nayri Wingara, Australian Indigenous Governance Institute and Lowitja Institute, 2023)

Our culture, our future: Report on Australian Indigenous cultural and intellectual property (Janke, T. 1998). This report 'details the types of rights Indigenous people seek in relation to their cultures and considers the application of current laws. It also makes recommendations for a comprehensive range of measures for improving the level of protection, including legal and non-legal reforms.' (Janke, T. 1998).

The AIATSIS Code of Ethics for Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander Research outlines 'four principles that underpin ethical Australian Indigenous research; these are: Indigenous self-determination, Indigenous leadership, impact and value, and sustainability and accountability' (AIATSIS, 2020).

The Framework for Governance of Indigenous data for data governed within the Australian Public Sector, see aims to provide Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander people greater agency over government held data to better reflect their priorities and aspirations (Commonwealth of Australia, 2024).

The United Nations Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples (United Nations, 2007) establishes global standards for protecting Indigenous rights, including self-determination, cultural and intellectual property, control over Indigenous data, and research ethics, as well as rights to culture, identity, employment, health, and education.

Practical actions across the full data lifecycle that can be taken by researchers and research organisations, institutes, and repositories as allies to support Indigenous Data Governance which is the mechanism to enact Indigenous Data Sovereignty - examples include Jennings et al. (2022), O'Brien et al. (2024), and Lowitja Institute (n.d.).

Australian Research Data Commons

CONTACT

- ardc.edu.au
- +61 3 9902 0585
- contact@ardc.edu.au

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